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Peculiarities of economics and business studies in technological faculties

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study was the investigation of peculiarities related to the education of managerial competence and to the need of economics and business knowledge for engineering studies students. According to business representatives, many engineering graduates lack of managerial competence and knowledge of economics. The study was performed at Kaunas University of Technology (KTU). A complex investigation consisting of three parts, i.e., an evaluation of students' attitude, an academics' approach analysis and an estimation of the attitude of business representatives as potential employers for high school graduates, has been chosen. The need for economics and business courses for students studying in technological faculties, the features of psychological environment of economics and business studies in those faculties, as well as weaknesses and strengths of learning economics and business subjects were revealed during the research.

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INTRODUCTION

There have been widely discussed about a changeable nature of the studies in higher educational institution under the circumstances of information technologies development and economic globalisation in recent years. The study programs are responsively associated with the changes in labour market, so that the majority of business schools, universities and colleges declare significant differences in the study process. One of the most prime accents is the development of competency education [1], [2]. Competence is an expression of human qualification or ability to act conditioned by the individual's knowledge, skills, attitudes, personality features and values [3], [4]. A public talk with employers indicates that many engineering graduates lack of managerial competence and knowledge of economics. There are very few researches on this subject in Lithuania [5], [6]. Therefore, it is particularly important to find out the competency education problems that Lithuanian higher education institutions faces within the framework of engineering studies realization and with a special focus on the physical and psychological learning environment.

The present study aims to investigate the peculiarities of economics and business studies in technological faculties.

The objectives of the research:

1. To explore the need of economics and business subjects to engineering studies students.
2. To disclose the features of physical and psychological environment of economics and business modules studies in technological faculties.
3. To reveal the ways to improve the cooperation between students, academics and employers.

1. RESEARCH METHODS

The research was accomplished at Kaunas University of Technology in Lithuania. The data were collected with survey questionnaires in 2016. The method of the research includes a complex analysis: 1) the students' attitude to the need of business and economics studies, to learning and psychological environment in technological faculties and to the cooperation between students, academics and employers, 2) the academics' attitude to the need of economics and business knowledge for students studying in technological faculties, to learning and psychological environment in technological faculties and to the cooperation between students, academics and employers, 3) the attitude of business representatives to the need of business and economics studies for students of technological faculties, to the readiness of young professionals to the labour market and to the cooperation between students, academics and employers. The self-administered questionnaires were consisted of statements and questions. Respondents were asked to indicate levels of agreement with statements using a 5-point Likert scale, which provided following response options: "1 = Disagree", "2 = More disagree than agree", "3 = Neither agree nor disagree", "4 = More agree than disagree", "5 = Agree". Questions

based on Likert scale allow to get more useful for the research information and to reduce the amount of questions.

Paniott's formula (1) has been used to calculate sample size (number of respondents), i.e., to ensure reliability of research of 95%:

$$n = 1/ (\Delta^2 + 1/N), \tag{1}$$

Where:

n – Sample size;

Δ – Allowed calculation error;

N – Size of population.

Statistical analysis of research results was conducted by employing the software of statistical data processing, *SPSS* (v23.0) and *Microsoft Excel* (2010).

2. RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

2.1. Students' approach

Purposeful sampling has been used for the formation of an investigative group. Individuals that are most representative in regard of an investigative feature were selected to the formative group. There were involved students studying Engineering Economics (economics subject) and Fundamental of Corporate Management (management subject) in the technological faculties of KTU. The subject of Engineering Economics was chosen by 122 students in the spring semester. The subject of Fundamental of Corporate Management was chosen by 150 students in the spring semester. 170 students, studying in the Faculty of Chemical Technology and in the Faculty of Mechanical Engineering and Design, participated in the investigation (170 questionnaires were handed out). The survey questionnaire was divided into three parts. First part was designed for the evaluation of the need for economics and business studies in technological faculties. Second part was made for the evaluation of learning and psychological environment of economics and business studies. Third part was designed for the study of students and employers relations.

2.1.1. Evaluation of the need for economics and business studies

For the evaluation of the need for economics and business studies in technological faculties, the students were asked whether they would like to study more economics and business subjects. The distribution of responses is shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. The need for economics and business subjects, in percent

A large proportion of students would like to study more economics and business subjects. They took the view that it is necessary for their future career and for the integration into the labour market. It is important to evaluate the expectations of students by offering economics and business subjects. The next question was designed to find out whether students have gained the additional competences in studying economics and business subjects. In students' opinion, the studies of economics and business subjects provided the additional competences like a perception of economic terms, common knowledge about an economy and market, and the ability to prepare a business plan. 54% of the respondents believed that it will be easier to take decisions after the studies of economics and business. 61% of the respondents stated that they gained knowledge that would let them to deal with economic and business problems. 52% of the respondents maintained that they have learned to prepare a business plan. 57% of the respondents gained knowledge that will be possible to apply in their specialities.

2.1.2. Evaluation of learning and psychological environment of economics and business studies

For the evaluation of learning and psychological environment of economic and business studies the statements describing these environments were submitted to students. The statements have been made with reference to other authors' [7], [8] researches about the educational environment and its impact on study results. The results of this research indicated that the engineering studies students rated the learning and psychological environment of economic and business studies quite positively. The students took the view that they are physically and psychologically safe during time of lectures. Students have been communicated with academics by email, during outing-lectures to companies, at the time of Medium or KTU events and during time-out between lectures. Most of the students would like to make more contact with academics in the informal environment, i.e., to drink coffee and to discuss on economic and business issues. Students would like more sports holidays, cycling races, orienteering contest and etc.

2.1.3. Students' attitude towards the communication with employers

The purpose of the study of relationship between students and employers was to find out whether the communication with business representatives is relevant for students and what forms of communication are most acceptable for them. The results showed that there are necessary students' meetings with business representatives during the study process. 66.5% of the respondents stated that the communication with business representatives has allowed a better understanding of the practical things. 47.1% of the respondents had it that such meetings have revealed new business opportunities and new market trends. 58.2% of the respondents maintained that such meetings have allowed for better understanding of employer needs and requirements for employees. 58.2% of the interviewees communicated with business respondents during lectures, 62% – at the time of the excursions to company, 14.7% – at the time of business plan contest. The students suggested the following possible communication with business forms as joint projects, product development (business representatives' participation in the process of study), students' projects mentoring, excursions to companies, practical lectures of business representatives, practice.

2.2. Academics approach

10 academics from Kaunas University of Technology participated in the survey. The academics, who were involved in the research, teach Chemistry, Design, Mechanics, Mathematics, Informatics, Electrical and Electronics, Energy and Construction.

2.2.1. Evaluation of the need of economics and business knowledge for engineering students

First and foremost, the aim of the survey was to find out academics' attitude to the teaching of economics and business disciplines in technological faculties. The opinion of academics participated in the study on this point is represented in Figure 2. There are shown the averages of the statements scored up accordance with a 5-point Likert scale. The academics, participated in the survey, had quite a solid positive opinion (average of scores was 4.6) on the need of economics and business knowledge to students studying in technological faculties.

Fig 2. Academics' approach to the need of economics and business knowledge to students studying in technological faculties, in scores

Most of survey participants (average of scores was 4.8) agreed that economics and business studies would provide students with additional competences such as team work skills, the ability to analyze the market situation, the fundamental of corporate financial management, the understanding how to develop a business project, the basic knowledge of business creation, establishment and etc. In opinion of academics, the students of technological faculties look kindly to the studies of economics and business (average of scores was 4), but moderately (average of scores was 3.4) master the knowledge of economics and business.

2.2.2. Evaluation of learning and psychological environment in technological faculties

The next part of survey was aimed for the evaluation learning and psychological environment in technological faculties in terms of teaching economics and business subjects. A proper communication between students and academics plays a significant role in the creating of good social-psychological climate in higher educational institution. However, academics did not have one opinion (average of scores was 2.9) whether students of technological faculties and lecturers teaching economics and business modules communicate after school time. It could be seen from the survey results that academics could not give unequivocal expression whether the informal communication between lecturer and student influences to better results of study subject (average of scores was 3.6). The respondents noted that informal communication between students and academics is available and can take a variety of mutually acceptable ways such as joint visits to companies, business plan contest, joint sports competition and etc. Talking of the adaptation of learning environment for the economics and business studies in technological faculties, the academics quite unanimously (average of scores was 4.1) stated on its relevance and applicability for these studies.

2.2.3. Academics' attitude towards the cooperation between students and employers

The further part of survey was aimed for the evaluation of the opinion of academics lecturing economics and business modules in technological faculties about cooperation with the business representatives at study time. The survey showed that there was given the opportunity to meet with business representatives at the time of economics or business lectures for the most of technological faculties' students (average of scores was 4.3). 90% of academics participated in the survey agreed that such cooperation between students and business representatives is useful. The academics noted the following possible cooperation forms as lectures of business representatives, excursions to companies, career days, business contest, joint events of students and business community and etc. The academics quite unanimously shared the opinion that it is required closer cooperation with the business community not only for students but also for lecturers. It is useful for preparing young professionals who will be in character with the ever-evolving requirements of the labour market. However, it should be noted that not all academics, teaching economics and business subjects in technological faculties, constantly communicate with business representatives (average of scores was 3.8). The academics pointed out the following cooperation ways as lecturer traineeships in companies, roundtable discussions, joint projects, cooperation in the formulation of the topics for course and final works, the solution of real business problems with the participation of students, academics and business community, and etc.

2.3. Business representatives' approach

The purpose of business expert survey was to evaluate the approach of business representatives to the need of business and economics studies for the students of technological faculties, to identify the psychological readiness of students to meet the challenges of the labour market and to find out the ways for the intensification of students and teaching staff cooperation with the business community. 8 experts participated in the research from different companies who hire engineers.

2.3.1. Evaluation of the need of economics and business knowledge for students studying in technological faculties

First and foremost, the aim of the survey was to find out the attitude of business experts to the need of economics and business knowledge for engineering students. The expert opinion on this subject is shown in Figure 3.

Fig 3. Business representatives' approach to the need of economics and business subjects for engineering students, in scores

The business representatives quite unanimously (average of scores was 4.9) agreed that the knowledge of economics and business fundamental is necessary for the students studying in technological faculties. 100% of business representatives agreed that such knowledge would provide the students with additional competencies. Experts pointed out that the teaching of business and economics subjects enables students to acquire knowledge, which are necessary for the development and marketing of products. In the opinion of the business representatives, such professionals could have a higher chance to take key positions where needed not only professional but also managerial skills. Even if a technical creative work is more acceptable for professional, the understanding how money appear in the company's account and the knowledge of basic economic calculations increase their competencies. The experts pointed out that such staff more objectively looks at their functions and at business, faster and deeper understands the market processes, and the management of business processes. Also they are able to hold forth ideas. That helps them to climb up the career ladder.

2.3.2. Evaluation of the readiness of young professionals to the labour market

The next part of survey was aimed for the evaluation of the opinion of business representatives about the readiness of young professionals to the labour market. According to the business experts, most of the technological studies graduates have the sufficient proficiency knowledge (average of scores was 3.8), which they are able to apply in practice. But more often employers desiderate other competencies of young professionals. Mostly employers desiderate communication skills, good usage of Lithuanian language and courage in making independent decisions. An insufficient knowledge of business and economics, which is an integral part of any business, was mentioned between wants. The business representatives rated ambiguously (average of scores was 3.1) the statement that high school graduates are psychologically ready to take various challenges at work. The analysis of the employers' approach revealed that the young specialist's work opportunities are usually limited by the lack of practical skills and personal characteristics. The majority of young people do not have personal purposes related to the professional activity and are minded to change workplaces. The issues of young professionals' motivation and education of personal motivation, i.e., self-control and pursuit of the objects, remain relevant for employers.

2.3.3. Business representatives' attitude towards the cooperation between students and employers

The further part of survey was aimed for the evaluation of the respondents' approach to the need of cooperation with students and lecturers. The business experts agreed that the cooperation between students and business representatives is essential on purpose to improve the readiness of future employees. The forms of cooperation may be various as lectures of business representatives, student visits to companies, business contest, practice in the company, career days, analysis of case studies, creative workshops, Brain Fights and etc. It is very important cooperation of business community not only with students but also with academics for better understanding the needs for the labour market. All of business representatives agreed with this point. They offered the following cooperation ways as academics' visits to companies and business managers visits to universities; joint projects; academics' involvement in creative workshops organised in companies; Brain Fights; University Open Days; the business section in University's Web page and etc. The business experts noted that it is important to act, i.e., to cooperate in any form.

3. CONCLUSIONS

According to the accomplished research the majority of students are satisfied that they have economics and business studies and would like more subjects that educate and motivate their competency of entrepreneurship. This approach was accepted by academics and employers also. With reference to the results of the evaluation of psychological environment, it can be stated that students are enough satisfied and feel psychologically well studying economics and business subjects. A good psychological climate during time of lectures helps to master the study material much better. The performed survey revealed that the majority of engineering graduates have sufficient knowledge of speciality, but their employment opportunities are limited by the lack of practical skills, economics and business knowledge. In summarising the employers' attitude to the young professionals, it can be stated that new graduates lack of common competences as skills of introducing themselves, communication skills, courage in making independent decisions. In addition, according to the business representatives, most of them do not have personal ambitions with a professional activity and are minded to change workplaces frequently. The issues of motivation, the pursuit of the objects and self-control of young professionals remain relevant for employers and for higher education establishments. The importance of economics and business studies in technological faculties was endorsed.

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